

Measuring Regional Attractiveness in Europe Through Spatio-Temporal Mobility Patterns

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Abstract

Regional attractiveness plays a crucial role in shaping spatial mobility, economic development, and population dynamics across Europe. Traditional approaches to measuring attractiveness rely on static indicators such as GDP, infrastructure, and amenities, providing an estimate of potential desirability rather than observed attractiveness. This study introduces a behaviorally grounded, spatio-temporal approach by analyzing realized human mobility flows across European NUTS2 regions, incorporating seven distinct types of movement: permanent migration, long-term and short-term student mobility, seasonal work, long-distance commuting, cross-border commuting, and multilocal living. By integrating heterogeneous data sources, including Labour Force Survey records, Erasmus mobility data, and Twitter-derived movement trajectories, we apply computational methods to quantify regional attractiveness. We operationalize this using two complementary approaches: an aggregate normalized net migration index and a Principal Component Analysis (PCA)-based attractiveness index. These spatially-explicit indicators capture both the intensity and diversity of regional inflows and outflows. Our results reveal strong spatial patterns, with urban centers consistently emerging as highly attractive, while regional anomalies, particularly in Nordic areas, highlight the significance of non-permanent mobility forms such as seasonal work and multilocal living. This emphasizes the limitations of potential-based indicators in understanding real-world mobility dynamics. By incorporating diverse mobility types and leveraging large-scale spatio-temporal data, this study advances movement analysis in regional science and supports more dynamic, data-driven approaches to modeling regional attractiveness. The findings have critical implications for spatial decision support, highlighting the need to integrate realized mobility data into regional planning and policy frameworks.

Keywords: Regional Attractiveness, Spatio-Temporal Mobility, Movement Analysis, Migration, GeoAI, Spatial Planning, Regional Development

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